

**CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES,
ENSURING QUALITY OF EDUCATION**

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Abstract. The main modern technologies aimed at ensuring quality education are characterized by transition. The article discusses innovations aimed at ensuring the quality of education, modern technologies aimed at improving the quality of education.

Keywords: quality of education, technology, interactive, system, feature, modeling.

Currently, many technologies are described in the literature. In order to better understand the nature of technologies, it is important to find reasons for their organization and systematization. Various authors suggest as such bases: target settings, content of teaching, nature of interaction between teacher and students, method of managing students' knowledge activities, scope of application.

The main modern technologies aimed at ensuring quality education are characterized by transition:

- from learning as a function of memorization to learning as a process of mental development that allows you to use what you have learned;
- from a purely associative, static model of knowledge to dynamically structured systems of mental actions;
- from focusing on the average student to differentiated and individualized educational programs;
- from external motivation for learning to internal moral-will regulation.

Today, the principle of variability has been announced in education, which makes it possible to choose and design the pedagogical process according to any model, including author's models. At the same time, it is important to establish a unique dialogue between different pedagogical systems and teaching technologies, to test new forms in practice.

The effectiveness of a particular technology largely depends on who implements certain approaches in teaching practice. A modern teacher, as a technologist of the educational process, should freely use a wide range of innovative technologies and not waste time to discover what is known. Today, it is impossible to become a pedagogically competent specialist without learning all the comprehensive arsenal of educational technologies.

The most popular and widely used are: person-oriented education and educational technology, pre-profile training and specialized educational technologies, project activities, flexible educational system, developmental education, integration, education discussion forms, game technologies, classroom technology, free education, information and computer technologies, group activity technology, game technologies, problem-based learning, educational research technology, various types of independent work technologies of students .

Non-standard forms of organizing educational lessons (lesson-game, lesson-competition, lesson-excursion, lesson-trip, multimedia lesson) to develop cognitive activity, increase the

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educational motivation of schoolchildren and ensure the quality of education, lesson-conference, business game, lesson-quiz, lesson-lecture, teleconference, lesson-performance, lesson-debate).

One of the modern technologies aimed at improving the quality of education is interactive education.

The advantages of interactive forms of education are clear, because:

- students learn new material not as passive listeners, but as active participants in the learning process;
- the share of class load decreases and the amount of independent work increases;
- students acquire the skills of mastering modern technical means and technologies of information search, retrieval and processing;
- the ability to independently find information and determine its level of reliability is formed.

Interactive technologies make it possible to establish permanent (planned) communication between teachers and students, rather than occasionally. They personalize education. It is important to understand that the use of network resources should not exclude direct communication between teachers and students.

Using interactive forms is really effective when needed. Any technology should have certain characteristics depending on the age of the students and the content of the material being studied.

Technology requirements in the elementary classroom may include:

- use of various technologies for classroom-free education - assessment system without grades in primary school, teaching children to assess themselves and their peers, freedom of choice of assessment system for schools;
- expansion of activity-based forms of education, which provide priority development of creative and research activities in all aspects of school life, including teaching;
- construction of the educational process using technologies for the organization of educational cooperation - significantly expanding the types of joint activities of students, their communicative experience in joint activities, gradual transition from oral to written types of communication, including information technologies use of opportunities;
- the use of game technologies that contribute to solving the main educational tasks in the lesson.

In mainstream school, the requirements must change. The basis of the interests and needs of adolescents is aimed at testing their capabilities in various areas: intellectual, social, interpersonal, personal. In this regard, the technological aspect of the main school should be to increase the variety of types and forms of organizing student activities. Thus, the main requirements for the organization of the educational process at this stage of school education may be:

- to increase project, individual and collective activity of schoolchildren;
- use of various forms of modular or concentrated training;
- strengthening the role of independent work of students with various data sources and databases;
- introduction of social practice and social design;
- differentiation of educational environment: workshop, laboratory, library, lecture hall;
- transition to a cumulative evaluation system, for example, using the "portfolio" technology.

In high school, the main idea should be to significantly expand the ability of each student to choose educational programs offered to him or to create his own personal educational program.

When choosing educational technologies for secondary school, it is recommended to follow two situations:

- giving preference to technologies that differentiate and individualize the learning process in one class without using selection tools;
- technologies for the development of independent cognitive activity play a very important role at this stage of education.

When formulating the requirements for the selection of educational technologies for each of the three levels, it should be taken into account that all technologies used in school education must have a certain continuity, and there are technologies that work effectively at only one level of education. It's not. The system of educational technologies should be created taking into account the main goals of each educational level.

affecting the quality of education. Innovation in education is the process of improving pedagogical technologies, which is one of the important components of the educational activity of any educational institution, a set of methods, methods and teaching tools.

Pedagogical innovations - innovations in the field of pedagogy, purposeful progressive changes that introduce stable elements (innovations) into the educational environment that improve the specific characteristics of both its individual components and the entire educational system.

Pedagogical innovations include both the educational system's own resources (intensive development path) and additional resources (investments) - new tools, equipment, technologies, capital investments, etc. (extensive development path) can also be done by engaging.

Taking into account the system of basic concepts of pedagogical innovation, RN Yusufbekova defines three blocks in the structure of innovative processes in a modern school.

The first block is the block of creating new things in pedagogy. Here we will consider such categories as innovation in pedagogy, classification of pedagogical innovations, conditions for creating something new, criteria for innovation, criteria for its development and readiness for use, traditions and innovations, stages. creating new things in pedagogy and creators of the new.

The second block is the block of perception, assimilation and evaluation of new things: teaching team, assessment and types of learning new things, conservatives and innovators in pedagogy, innovative environment, readiness of the teaching team to perceive and evaluate new things. things.

The third block is the block of using and applying new things. This unit explores the forms and types of introduction, use and application of new things.

Innovations aimed at ensuring the quality of education should be related to the following changes:

- goals, content, methods and technologies, forms of organization and management system;
- Pedagogical activity style and organization of educational and cognitive process;
- the system of monitoring and evaluating the level of education;
- financing system;
- educational and methodological provision;
- system of educational work;
- in the curriculum and educational programs;
- in the activities of the teacher and the student.

In this regard, all innovations in the field of education can be classified as follows:

1. Innovations within the subject: innovations within the subject based on the specifics of its teaching.

2. General methodological innovations: the introduction of non-traditional pedagogical technologies of a universal character into teaching practice, as they can be used in any field of science.

3. Administrative innovations are decisions taken by managers at different levels that help the effective functioning of all subjects of educational activity.

4. Ideological innovation: the renewal of consciousness, the fundamental basis of all other innovations caused by the trends of the times.

Pedagogical innovations can be pedagogical ideas, processes, tools, methods, forms, technologies, content programs, etc.

Pedagogical innovations can be classified as follows:

1) by type of activity :

- pedagogic, provider of the pedagogical process;
- providing management, innovative management of educational institutions;

2) according to the validity period :

- short term;
- Long term;

3) according to the nature of changes :

- based on radically new ideas and approaches;
- combined on the basis of a new combination of certain elements;
- changed based on improvement and addition of existing samples and forms;

4) according to the scope of changes :

- change of local, that is, separate departments or components that are independent from each other;

- modular – interconnected groups of several local innovations;
- systemic - a complete reconstruction of the entire system.

Pedagogical innovations are carried out according to a certain algorithm. We can highlight the following Stages of development and implementation of pedagogical innovations:

1. Identifying the need for innovation - developing criteria and indicators of the state of the pedagogical system to be reformed.

2. Determining the need for reform - comprehensive inspection and evaluation of the quality of the pedagogical system, preparation of special tools.

3. Look for examples of advanced pedagogical solutions that can be used to model innovation.

4. Analysis of scientific developments, including creative solutions to current pedagogical problems.

5. Designing an innovative model of the entire pedagogical system or its individual parts.

6. Determining tasks, assigning responsibilities, looking for solutions, establishing forms of control.

7. Calculation of practical importance and efficiency.

8. Construction of the innovation implementation algorithm - search for areas to be renewed or replaced, modeling of innovations, development of an experimental program, monitoring of its results, implementation of necessary corrections, final control.

9. Revising and updating the professional vocabulary, that is, introducing new concepts into the professional vocabulary.

10. Protecting pedagogical innovation from copying the innovative teacher's creative method without creative processing.

teaching technologies, on the one hand, allows students to improve the efficiency of mastering educational material, and on the other hand, allows teachers to pay more attention to the issues of individual and personal growth of students. , enables quality control. providing education and their creative development.

Innovative educational technologies increase the work efficiency of teachers. The monitoring and feedback system of each student's learning activity allows to prepare students according to their individual capabilities and character. For example, one student can master the material for the first time, while another can sit at the computer and work through the material two or three times or more. Transferring the main function of teaching to educational tools frees up the teacher's time, as a result of which he can pay more attention to the issues of individual and personal development of students. The goal for innovative technology is defined very clearly, so the use of objective control methods allows reducing the role of the subjective factor in control; creation of innovative teaching technologies allows to reduce dependence on the educational process. the result according to the qualification level of the teacher. Technologization creates necessary conditions for solving the problem of continuity of educational programs of school education.

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